

Available online freely at www.isisn.org

Bioscience Research

Print ISSN: 1811-9506 Online ISSN: 2218-3973

Journal by Innovative Scientific Information & Services Network

RESEARCH ARTICLE

BIOSCIENCE RESEARCH, 2018 15(4):4171-4183.

OPEN ACCESS

Novel antifungal bacteriocin from *Lactobacillus paracasei* KC39 with anti-mycotoxigenic properties.

Mohamed Gamal Shehata¹, Ahmed Noah Badr^{2*}, and Sobhy Ahmed El Sohaimy¹

¹Department of Food Technology, Arid Lands Cultivation Research Institute, City of Scientific Research and Technological Application, Alexandria, **Egypt**

²Department of Food Toxicology and Contaminants, National Research Centre, Dokki 12622, Cairo, **Egypt**

*Correspondence: noohbadr@gmail.com Accepted: 15 Oct.2018 Published online: 30 Dec. 2018

Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) have a record of the bio-preservatives application in food. This investigation was targeted to isolate and identify the antifungal potency of *Lactobacillus paracasei* KC39 from a traditional Egyptian cheese (Kareish). Furthermore, to estimate, purify, and describe the new bacteriocin characteristics and evaluate its detoxification impact particularly for mycotoxin. Isolated *Lb. paracasei* from Kareish cheese supernatant tested for bacteriocin production. The novel bacteriocin (KC39) was purified by a three-step purification procedure using NGC protein purification system. The supernatant was evaluated totally then its fractionations were examined for antimicrobial, antifungal, and anti-mycotoxigenic properties against *Aspergillus parasiticus* ITEM11, *Aspergillus carbonarius* ITEM 5010 and its excreted mycotoxin. Mycotoxins degradation by different supernatant fractionations evaluated using HPLC apparatus. The different fractionation of bacterial metabolite declared the existence of the novel bacteriocin. Bacteriocin KC39 exhibited a wide range of antifungal activity. Bacteriocin KC39 is the first excreted compound of *Lb. paracasei* reported inhibiting toxigenic fungi growth. The molecular mass of KC39 bacteriocin recorded 3337 Da by MALDI-TOF-MS analyses. The bacteriocin KC39 characteristics declared its potential bio preservative of food and application value in the food sector. The obtained results of the current study have opened the possibility of future potential bacteriocin KC39 biotechnological applications and its strain producer as bio preservatives, dairy culture starter, and safety improvement of food versus the susceptible fungal infection.

Keywords: Antifungal, *Aspergillus*, bacteriocin, *Lactobacillus paracasei*, mycotoxin, protein purification.

INTRODUCTION

Food contaminations are the major hazard for the human health. Not only, the pathogen is the main hazard for food commodities that turned food into un-useful materials, but also, molds especially toxigenic fungi could participate in food contamination (Dagnas and Membré 2013, Sabry et al., 2016). Such spoilage can make a large economic loss, and additional toxicity by mycotoxins can cause public health problems (Schnürer and Magnusson 2005, Shahat et al., 2017). The present demand of natural preservation has stimulated the search for food

appropriate antimicrobials generated by microorganisms.

The antimicrobial compounds from LAB play a crucial function in overcoming food-borne pathogens (De Mynck et al., 2004). Furthermore, LAB have a great record of an application as bio preservatives for food and feed storage that are encouraging alternatives to chemical preservatives (Stiles 1996). Antifungal from LAB involves metabolites like protein, cyclic dipeptides, carboxylic acids and their derivatives (Ryan et al., 2011, Wang et al., 2012). Bacteriocins are antimicrobial peptides group produced by bacteria

to destroy or inhibit the growth of different types of microorganisms (Hassan et al., 2012).

Bacteriocins produced by various LAB have been constantly described (Anastasiadou et al., 2008, Kruger et al., 2013). Nisin, the first LAB bacteriocin, was reported in the previous century (Rogers 1928), and is presently acceptable for use in food preservative. Owing to the commonly recognized as the safe status of LAB, several LAB bacteriocin have possible applications in food manufacturing to prevent the foodborne pathogens (De Muyndck et al., 2004, Shehata et al., 2016).

However, research on antifungal LAB is still fewer and the majority only explains the inhibitory activities of LAB. Heretofore, limited studies were characterized or identified antifungal compounds and its mechanisms (Schnürer and Magnusson 2005). Furthermore, Yang and Chang (2010) stated that the metabolites excreted by *Lb. plantarum* could be successfully utilized for the same goal as an alternative antifungal of chemical preservatives.

This work was focused on the isolation and identification of antifungal activity of *Lb. paracasei* KC39 from Kareish cheese. Discovery of unique bacteriocin-producing strains beside the adequate quantities isolation of pure bacteriocin is subsequently important for food safety. The great challenge to avoid food risks is to prepare efficient controls, wanting to raise costs or to decrease the quality. Utilizing natural antimicrobials considered a modern application in food preservation which is the most efficient technique enhances food safety. Furthermore, the purification, characterization, and evaluation of the new bacteriocin for a detoxifying effect of mycotoxins was also an aim of this study.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Isolation of LAB strains

Domiaty and Kareish cheese were collected from Alexandria markets, Egypt. Samples were cultured using a sterilized re-constituted skim milk which incubated until coagulation. Coagulated samples were then streaked on De Man Rogosa and Sharp (MRS) media purchased from Difco, USA. Then it was incubated under anaerobic condition (30°C, 37°C, and 42°C / 48h) using the gaspak system (Oxoid Anaero Gen, Thermo Scientific).

Preparation of cell free supernatant (CFS)

LAB isolates were cultivated in MRS broth at 30°C/24 h. The culture was centrifuged at 9500xg / 15 min then it filter-sterilized through a 0.45µm Milli-pore filter. The cell-free filtrate was kept for the further experiments.

Fungi and spore suspension preparation

Mycotoxin-producing strains either *A. parasiticus* ITEM 11 or *A. Carbonarius* ITEM 5010 were obtained from Agro-Food Microbial Culture Collection (ITEM), Bari, Italy. These strains were cultured on yeast extract sucrose (YES) agar (28°C/ 8 days). The spore concentration was estimated by the haemocytometer, adjusted to 10⁶ spores/mL for the agar spot on lawn assay. After that; media were filtered to evaluate the fungal strain ability for mycotoxin excretion.

Antifungal activity assays

The spot-on-the lawn assay was applied to evaluate the antifungal activities according to the method by Hoover and Harlander (1993). Plates were prepared by adding the mold (10⁶ spores / 20 mL YES) to 1.5% (w/v) YES agar. A spore solution and the supernatant was prepared. For this screening, 10 µL of the sample were spotted onto the sensing mold plates. The plates were incubated at 30°C/ 48 h then examined for inhibition zones. Antifungal activity, expressed as arbitrary units (AU/mL), was defined as the reciprocal of the highest dilution at which fungal growth was inhibited. The antifungal titre was calculated as (1000/d) D, where D is dilution factor and d is the dose (the number of antifungal samples pipetted on each spot). Moreover, antifungal also evaluated using well diffusion assay. The plates were incubated at 30°C/ 48 h and examined for inhibition zones (Shehata et al., 2017; Abdel-Fattah et al., 2018).

Aflatoxin and Ochratoxin A production

YES media were utilized to Mycotoxin producing inoculated about 10⁶ spore (Badr et al. 2017a), for aflatoxin (AF) production; it incubated on 28°C/8 days half of this period flasks kept in the dark. However, for ochratoxin A (OCA) production from *A. carbonarius* ITEM 5010; it was done according to the method described by Wang et al., (2016).

Identification of LAB bacteriocin-producing

The strain which produced the new bacteriocin was identified by Gram stain and the

microscopically analysis, then identified using 16S rRNA technique. The 16S rRNA was amplified using PCR by universal primers (5'CCGAATTCGTCGACAACAGAGTTTGATCCTGGCTCAG3' and 5'CCCGGATCCAAGCTTAAGGAGGTGATCCA GCC3'). The PCR amplification was carried out in the thermo cycler PCR (Santa Clara, California, United States) according to the following program: initial denaturation (95°C/ 5min). Amplification (30 cycles, 95°C/40sec), annealing (55°C/40sec), extension (72°C/1min), followed by the final extension (72°C/10 min).

The gel image of separated products was taken using Syngene Bio Maging gel documentation system (Canada). The DNA marker 100–1500 bp (TAKARA BIO INC., Japan) was applied in the molecular weight standards. The final sequences were analyzed and assembled with NCBI (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>). A similarity in the sequence among isolated and related taxa were regained from GenBank using BLAST. The phylogenetic tree was estimated using the bootstrap analysis (1000 copies) using the software package, MEGA 4.0 (Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis, Version 4.0) and the neighbor-joining method (Tamura et al., 2004).

Effect of enzymes, heat treatment, and the pH on resultant bacteriocin

The effect of several enzymes on bacteriocin potency was evaluated as described by Noonpakdee et al., (2003) with slight modification. Two hundred microlitre of filter-sterilized cell-free supernatant was incubated with 20 µl of the following enzymes: proteinase K, trypsin, α-chymotrypsin, α-amylase, lipase at a final concentration of 0.1 mg/ml. The samples were incubated for 3 h at 37 °C. The reaction was then stopped by boiling for 5 min. For the heat treatment tests, the bacteriocin was incubated at 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90 and 100 °C for 15 min. The original pH of the bacteriocin was about pH 6.5 in aqueous solution. The pH sensitivity of the bacteriocin was performed at pH values of 2.0 to 11.0 at 37 °C for 2 h. After the treatment in different pH tests, the samples were readjusted to the original pH 6.5 to determine the effect of different pH on antifungal activity. The activity of the residual bacteriocin was estimated by spot on-lawn method against indicator *A. parasiticus* ITEM 11.

Kinetics of growth and bacteriocin production

MRS broth was inoculated with overnight culture (2%, v/v) of *Lb. paracasei* KC39 and incubated for 24 h /30°C under non-regulated pH conditions. At regular intervals (2h), the changes in optical density (600 nm). Concomitantly, each 2 h the antifungal activity (AU/mL) in CFS was calculated by spot-on-lawn method (Vijayakumar and Muriana 2015).

Crude bacteriocin preparation and partial purification

The CFS was prepared as described in Section (Preparation of cell free supernatant). Ammonium sulfate (80% saturate) was applied in precipitating the crude bacteriocin, after which this precipitated was dialyzed against ultrapure water at 4°C for desalting. Then the precipitated proteins were collected by centrifugation at 10,000g /20 min/ 4°C and dissolved in a minimal quantity of a 10 mM acetate buffer then dialyzed (16 h/4°C) against the same buffer with a 1-kDa pore size dialysis membrane (spectrum labs, USA).

Purification of bacteriocin

The dialyzed crude bacteriocin was purified by NGC chromatography system (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA) after filtration through a 0.45-µm-filter membrane. The Anion Exchange column (Enrich Q 5/50 mm) was equilibrated with Tris-HCl buffer (pH 8.8, 20 mM). Then, 100 µL of bacteriocin were loaded onto the pre-equilibrated column at a flow rate of 0.5 mL/min and washed with buffer Tris-HCl for 10 min. Then, elution was conducted using a linear gradient of 1 M NaCl (0–100%) at a flow rate of 0.5 mL/min. Each fraction was tested for antifungal activity and protein profiling by SDS-PAGE. The fraction that showed activity was lyophilized and suspended in 200 µL of 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 6.5) and then further purified by Size Exclusion column (ENrich SEC70, 10/300 mm). The elution was performed at a flow rate of 1 mL/min using an isocratic segments by Phosphate buffered saline within 100 min. Fractions were monitored at 280 nm and collected as 1 mL size of fractions (fraction collection, NGC™, Bio-Rad Laboratories, Inc., USA). The fractions were concentrated using lyophilizer and dissolved in Phosphate buffer (pH 6.0) and used in the bacteriocin activity assay and molecular mass determination (MALDI-TOF-TOF mass spectrometry- Bruker). The protein concentration was determined by the Bradford method (Altuntaş, 2014) with bovine serum albumin as standard.

Detoxification analysis of supernatant and different stages of purification of KC39 against toxigenic fungi

The spot-on-the lawn assay was applied for detecting the antifungal activities of each stage (Hoover and Harlander 1993).

Mycotoxins determination

Aflatoxin Extraction of YES media

One hundred milliliter of YES media containing the growth of *A. parasiticus* ITEM 11, 5g NaCl and 100 mL of a methanol: water (80:20, v/v) were blended at high speed for 1 min. The samples were filtered using filter paper and 10 mL of filtrates were diluted with 40 mL sterile double distilled water (Badr et al., 2017b).

Aflatoxin Clean-up:

About 10mL of filtered was passed via immune-affinity column (Afla-Test®, VICAM, Ma 01757, USA), the flow rate was 1-2 drops/sec. The column washed by purified water (2x10ml as 2 drops/sec). Elution was performed with 1.0 mL HPLC grade methanol.

Extraction of OCA from media:

The OTA that produced by *A. carbonarius* ITEM 5010 on liquid media was extracted by method of Bragulat et al., (2001)

Detection and quantification of OTA by HPLC:

The OTA was detected using HPLC, fluorescence detection (λ_{exc} , 330 nm; λ_{em} , 460 nm) (Waters 474), using a C18 column (Waters Spherisorb 5 μ m, ODS2, 4.6x250 mm). The mobile phase (acetonitrile-water-acetic acid, 57:41:2) at flow-rate 1.0 mL/min. The injection volume was 25 μ L, retention time was 7 min. The detection limit of the analysis was 0.01 μ g/g OTA. Quantification was achieved by a computing integrator (Millenium-32 v. 3.05 software, Milford, Massachusetts, USA).

Aflatoxin analysis by HPLC:

The HPLC system used for AF estimation was an Agilent 1200 series system (Agilent, Technologies Inc. USA) supported by a FLD G1321A fluorescence detector and ALS G1329A auto sampler, Degasser G1379B. Bin Bump G1312A and a C18 (150x4.6 mm) column joined to a pre-column (4x3-mm cartridge, Phenomenex Luna). The mobile phase was water: acetonitrile: methanol; 3:1:1 v/v/v), flow rate of

1mL/min/360nm excitation and 420nm emission wavelengths.

Statistical analysis

All experiment results were performed in replicates. It was represent as means \pm standard deviation. Significant differences among mean calculated using SPSS 16.0 software (P=0.05).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Isolation and identification of Kareish bacteria and antifungal evaluation

A total of 76 LAB isolated from Domiatti and Kareish cheese and their CFSs were examined for antifungal activity using the agar spot assay. Twelve strains out of 76 showed an efficiently impact to reduce microorganisms growth. Mainly the supernatant of these twelve strains recorded a good impact against food pathogenic strains like *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Bacillus cereus*, and *Staphylococcus aureus* (Data not shown). These positively effective strains are presented in (Table 1). The CFS of these twelve isolates (named KD3, KD8, KD16, KD23, KD27, KC2, KC11, KC12, KC30, KC34, KC39, and KC40,) had distinct antifungal activity against two strains of toxigenic fungi, *A. parasiticus* ITEM 11 and *A. Carbonarius* ITEM 5010, which had the ability to produce mycotoxins.

The results reported that, there was efficiency of the twelve strains against the AF producing fungi of *A. parasiticus* ITEM 11. The strains KC12, KD 3, KD 16, and KD 23 showed low anti-fungal against Aflatoxigenic fungi, however KC39 was the most effective strains that recorded as the highest inhibition impact on *Aspergillus parasiticus* ITEM 11 (6400 AU/ml). Isolated bacteria (12 strains) was examined to inhibit OCA producing-fungi strain, *Aspergillus carbonarius* ITEM 5010. Five strains recorded non-effective, while three strains showed high antifungal role included strain KC 39 which recorded the best and effective strain against *A. carbonarius* ITEM 5010. According to the previous research, some bacteria produce several peptides that could act a great function against harmful microorganisms (Yan et al., 2007, O'Shea et al., 2012). These peptides could be applied in food manufacture for increasing the safety (Verschuere et al., 2000, De Vuyst and Leroy 2007). Most LAB have an antifungal activity depending on its metabolites excretion in media (Schnürer and Magnusson 2005).

Table (1): Antifungal activities of cell-free supernatants of 12 LAB isolates against *A. parasiticus* ITEM 11 and *A. carbonarius* ITEM 5010

Isolate No.	Isolate code	<i>A. parasiticus</i> ITEM 11 (AU/ml)*	<i>A. carbonarius</i> ITEM 5010 (AU/ml)*
1.	KD3	800	0
2.	KD8	1600	0
3.	KD16	800	0
4.	KD23	800	0
5.	KD27	3200	3200
6.	KC2	1600	3200
7.	KC11	3200	800
8.	KC12	800	0
9.	KC30	1600	1600
10.	KC34	1600	800
11.	KC39	6400	6400
12.	KC40	3200	3200

* **AU/ml**: Arbitrary units/ml cell-free supernatant was calculated according to the following equation: $(1000/d) \times D$. Where **D** is the two-fold dilution factor, **d** is the amount of supernatant used.

Toxicogenic fungi which included *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, *Mucor*, *Fusarium*, and *Candida* reported affecting by these bacterial substances. However, the source of most active bacteria was mainly from fermented products (Gupta and Srivastava 2014, Lee and Chang 2016, Luz et al., 2017, Kwak et al., 2018).

Isolation and identification of the bacteriocin-producing isolate *Lb. paracasei* KC 39.

Again, among the twelve effective bacterial isolates, KC39 showed stronger antifungal activity than other eleven isolates. For this reason strain KC39 was selected for further analysis. On the basis of microscopy analysis, isolate KC39 was found to be Gram-positive and presented as single rods or short chains. *Lb. paracasei* strain KC39 was gained a new name according to its accession number; its name became *Lb. paracasei* MG847589. A partial 16S rRNA gene sequence (~1200 bp) of strain KC39 was obtained and compared with those available in GenBank/EMBL/DDBJ nucleotide sequence database. It was revealed that the novel isolate belongs to the family *Lactobacillaceae*, order *Lactobacillales* and class *Bacilli*. The closest relatives were *Lactobacillus* spp. (>99% similarity). A neighbor-joining phylogenetic tree (Fig. 1) shows close clustering with the genus *Lactobacillus* spp., and a high homology rate with *Lb. paracasei* BL16-1(99.0%); *Lb. casei* WS13(99.0%). Since these closely related species also exhibit high 16S rRNA gene sequence similarities ($\geq 99\%$) (Mao et al., 2015), there is a possibility that strain KC39 represents a novel species. However, at the previous studies

on the closest strains (*Lb. casei*) of our isolate showed a good activity against harmful material. It was reported a protection versus the AF oxidative stress in the biological system (Hathout et al., 2011). Again, number of *Lb. casei* species reported to produce an antifungal compounds according to their activities in many substrates (Atanassova et al., 2003, Manzoni et al., 2006, Hassan and Bullerman 2008). At this point, the excreted metabolite from this isolate needs to be clearer either for its structure or its bioavailability and bioactivity.

Characteristics and composition of the antifungal compounds produced by *Lb. paracasei* KC39

When the *Lb. paracasei* KC39 supernatant was neutralized at pH 7.0, the inhibitory activity against *A. parasiticus* ITEM 11 decreased from 6400 to 3200 AU/mL, but the activity eliminated at pH 11 (Table 2). This pH-dependent antifungal potency was similar to the earlier studies (Sathe et al., 2007, Laref and Guessas 2013, Cortés-Zavaleta et al., 2014). The antifungal proteinaceous compounds of *Lb. paracasei* KC39 disappeared or decreased with proteolytic enzymes, including proteinase K, α -chymotrypsin and trypsin. Similarly, the activity remained stable after the treatments of different enzymes, including lipase and α -amylase. The bacteriocin recorded a heat tolerant properties, stable up to 70°C/15 min, but the activity eliminated at 100°C/15 min.

Kinetics of bacteriocin production

The inhibition activity of bacteriocin increased

rapidly in the growth broth after 24 h of incubation, close to the end of the logarithmic growth phase (Fig. 2). Maximum inhibition activity (represent in an inhibition zone) was observed at 20 h. This corresponded to the middle of the stationary phase, and it declined slowly after 20 h of incubation until the end of testing at 24 h. The bacteriocins extract from *Lb. paracasei* KC39 showed higher antifungal activity against *A. parasiticus* ITEM 11 after 20 h of incubation (Fig. 2).

Purification of bacteriocin

The CFS of *Lb. paracasei* KC39 containing bacteriocin (6400 AU/mL) was purified by protein purification system using ion exchange chromatography and gel filtration chromatography. Bacteriocin was precipitated by ammonium sulfate 80% saturation, the crude bacteriocin was dialyzed at 4 °C for desalting. After desalting, ion exchange column was utilized

for purification and four peaks were found (Fig 3A.), in which fourth peaks had antifungal activity. Active fraction of the ion exchange that was pooled and gave a specific activity of 432.43 AU per mg with 12.16 fold purification (Table 3). Subsequently, the ion exchange fractions was concentrated and further applied on gel filtration column, by which seven fractions were gained with an antifungal activity (Fig. 3 B). The active fraction was checked by gel filtration column, in which only one peak appeared and considered as a pure bacteriocin. The purified bacteriocin was designated as bacteriocin KC39. The purified bacteriocin was pooled and lyophilized and subjected to SDS-PAGE for analyzing its purity and molecular mass. The protein concentration was determined by the Bradford method (Altuntaş et al. 2014).

Figure. 1. Phylogenic relationships based on 16S rRNA sequences of *Lactobacillus paracasei* KC39 isolates

Figure 2. Kinetics of growth (■) and bacteriocin production (Blue bar) during the growth of *Lactobacillus paracasei* KC39 in MRS media at 30 °C.

Table (2): Effect of various proteolytic enzymes, catalase, α -amylase, lipase, pH, and temperature on antifungal activity of the cell free supernatant of *Lactobacillus paracasei* KC39 against *A. parasiticus* ITEM 11

Cell free supernatant treatment	Remaining activity (AU /ml)*	Reduction (%)
Control	6400	0
Enzyme (1mg/ml)		
Catalase (pH 7.0)	3200	50
α -amylase	3200	50
Lipase	3200	50
Proteinase K	0	100
Trypsin	1600	75
α -chymotrypsin	3200	50
pH		
2	3200	50
3	3200	50
4	3200	50
5	3200	50
6	3200	50
7	3200	50
8	3200	50
9	1600	75
10	1600	75
11	0	100
Temperatures		
40	6400	0
50	6400	0
60	6400	0
70	6400	0
80	3200	50
90	1600	75
100	0	100

* AU/ml: Arbitrary units/ml cell-free supernatant was calculated according to the following equation: $(1000/d) \times D$
 Where D is the two-fold dilution factor, d is the amount of supernatant used.

Table (3): Purification of antifungal compounds produced by *Lactobacillus paracasei* KC39.

Purification stages	Vol. (mL)	Bacteriocin Activity (AU/mL)*	Total protein (mg)	Specific Activity (AU/mg)	Recovery (%)	Purification (fold)
Culture supernatant	2000	6400	180	35.55	100	1
Crude $(NH_4)_2SO_4$ precipitate –conc.75	20	12800	143	89.51	200	2.52
Ion exchange	10	1600	3.7	432.43	25	12.16
Gel filtration	3	800	0.96	833.30	12.5	23.4

* AU/ml: Arbitrary units/ml cell-free supernatant was calculated according to the following equation: $(1000/d) \times D$
 Where D is the two-fold dilution factor, d is the amount of supernatant used.

Figure. 3. Purification of bacteriocin produced by *Lactobacillus paracasei* KC39 by chromatography (A: ion exchange chromatography & B: gel filtration chromatography).

Figure. 4. SDS-PAGE of bacteriocin KC39 purified by NGC protein purification system. M, molecular weight markers; 1, Crude $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ precipitate; 2, Ion exchange; 3, Gel filtration.

Purification and molecular mass determination of bacteriocin KC39

The purified bacteriocin was subjected to SDS-PAGE and only a single band was detected after gel filtration with molecular weight of 3.37 KDa, which confirm a highly purified bacteriocin. (Fig 4). The molecular mass of the purified peptide and bacteriocin KC39 were confirmed by MALDI-TOF/MS analysis, while bacteriocin KC39 was determined at 3337 Da (Fig 5). The obtained results emphasized that the purified bacteriocin KC39 is different from previous studied bacteriocins LiN333, DU10, SMXD51 and MN047 which had a molecular weight of 4890 Da, 6313 Da, 5383.2 Da and 1770 Da, respectively (Perumal et al., 2016, Ullah et al., 2017). The purified bacteriocin from *L. paracasei* KC39 is completely novel active peptide, which open a new prospect in food safety to control food fungal contamination.

Previously studied bacteriocins had not the similar molecular weights, including bacteriocins from *Lactobacillus coryniformis* XN8, LXA

of 3100.02 Da (Yi et al., 2016), enterocin LD3 of 4114.6 Da (Gupta et al., 2016), plantaricin K25 of 2000Da (Wen et al., 2016), and LXA of 3100.02 Da (Yi et al., 2016). To the best of our knowledge, no previous studies were reported an active bacteriocin with a molecular weight of 3373 Da, which confirm again the novelty of bacteriocin KC39 according to its molecular mass (Fig. 5).

Antifungal and anti-mycotoxigenic impact of different steps of bacteriocin fractionation of KC39

The inhibition impact of the CFS and bacteriocin fractions on mycotoxin were evaluated on two types of mycotoxins that excreted by two toxigenic fungi strains. These fungi were *A. parasiticus* ITEM 11 which produce Aflatoxin B1 (AFB1) and *A. carbonarius* ITEM 5010 which produce OCA. The mycotoxin inhibition by bacteriocin fractions was recorded in **Table (4)**. The highest reducing ratio was recorded for the whole supernatant either for AFB1 or for OCA.

Figure 5. MALDI-TOF MS of the purified bacteriocin revealed a molecular mass of 3.374 KDa.
Note: MALDI-TOF MS, mass-assisted laser desorption ionization time of flight mass spectrometry.

Table (4): Inhibitory effect of novel bacteriocin from *Lactobacillus paracasei*KC39 on aflatoxin B₁ and ochratoxin A in YES medium.

Different fractions	Aflatoxin B ₁		Ochratoxin A	
	ng/ml	Reducing (%)	ng/ml	Reducing (%)
Control	180±1.1 ^a	% 0	50±1.8 ^a	0%
Supernatant	74±2.6 ^c	% 58.9	15.6±0.96 ^c	70%
Ammonium sulphate	131±2.7 ^b	% 27.2	24.5±1.3 ^b	51%
Ion exchange	134±1.7 ^b	% 25.5	24.2±1.1 ^b	51.6%
Gel filtration	123±2.4 ^b	% 31.7	24.1±0.97 ^b	51.8%

Anti-mycotoxigenic potency was evaluated as reducing of mycotoxin amount.

Antifungal effect was determined as loss in mycelia weight growth on yeast extract sucrose media

Data were represented as means of five replicates

Means within columns not sharing the same superscript are significantly different (p = 0.05)

Moreover, the bacteriocin fractions recorded so close ratio for inhibition by three types of fractions. The finding results were as the same direction of other earlier investigation, which has been done on the bacteriocin isolated from different bacterial strains. Hathout et al., (2011) mentioned the role of lactobacillus strains, which protect against oxidative stress in rats fed AF-contaminated diet. Also, a review that has been done by Dalié et al., (2010) point up to the expected function that happened by lactic acid bacteria to suppress mold growth as well as to reducing the amount of mycotoxin producing in the presence of lactic bacteria. Franco et al., (2011) reported an active function of LAB in the inhibition of *F. graminearum*, it was also had an ability to reduce deoxynivalenol mycotoxin amount. Otherwise, several studies were mentioned to the role of LAB in detoxification of several mycotoxin from food matrix (Schnürer and Magnusson 2005, Sathe et al., 2007).

CONCLUSION

Bacteria, particularly lactobacillus, were produced active components in the growth media. These components mostly classified into organic acids or peptides. Isolated bacterial strain from Egyptian traditional cheeses (Kariesh) was purified and identified by 16S rRNA technique as *Lb. paracasei* KC39. The crude supernatant showed antifungal characteristics. However, supernatant fractions were showed a high potency antifungal and anti-mycotoxigenic effect. The purified bacteriocin record a molecular weight of 3.37 kDa using MALDI-TOF MS analysis. The results opened the possibility of future potential biotechnological applications of bacteriocin KC39 as bio-preservatives and safety of susceptible

fungal infection food products. The novel active bacteriocin open a new prospect in food safety of reducing aflatoxins and ochratoxin contamination.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declared that present study was performed in absence of any conflict of interest.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to thank Dr. Antonio F. Logrieco, Institute of Science of Food Production (ISPA), National Research Council (CNR) for facilitates and support the research by the fungal strains.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

MGS isolated bacterial strains, perform the identification, SAE prepared and study the supernatant properties. MGS and ANB made the fractionation, study the antifungal characteristics, designed, and performed the experiment, also wrote the manuscript. MGS identified the isolated bacteriocin. ANB performed mycotoxin reduction evaluations. SAE statistically analyzed the results. ANB, SAE, and MGS read, reviewed, and accept the final manuscript.

Copyrights: © 2017 @ author (s).

This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author(s) and source are credited and that the original publication in this journal is cited, in accordance with accepted academic practice. No use, distribution or reproduction is permitted which does not comply

with these terms.

REFERENCES

- Abdel-Fattah, S. M., A. N. Badr, F. A. H. A. Seif, S. M. Ali and R. A. Hassan (2018). "Antifungal and anti-mycotoxigenic impact of eco-friendly extracts of wild stevia." *Journal of Biological Sciences* 18(8): 488-499.
- Altuntaş, E. G., K. Ayhan, S. Peker, B. Ayhan and D. Ö. Demiralp (2014). "Purification and mass spectrometry based characterization of a pediocin produced by *Pediococcus acidilactici* 13." *Molecular biology reports* 41(10): 6879-6885.
- Anastasiadou, S., M. Papagianni, G. Filiouis, I. Ambrosiadis and P. Koidis (2008). "Pediocin SA-1, an antimicrobial peptide from *Pediococcus acidilactici* NRRL B5627: Production conditions, purification and characterization." *Bioresource Technology* 99(13): 5384-5390.
- Atanassova, M., Y. Choiset, M. Dalgalarondo, J.-M. Chobert, X. Dousset, I. Ivanova and T. Haertlé (2003). "Isolation and partial biochemical characterization of a proteinaceous anti-bacteria and anti-yeast compound produced by *Lactobacillus paracasei* subsp. *paracasei* strain M3." *International journal of food microbiology* 87(1-2): 63-73.
- Badr, A. N., A. F. Logrieco, H. A. Amra and T. Hussein (2017a). "Ochratoxin a occurrence on Egyptian wheat during seasons (2009-2014)." *Asian Journal of Scientific Research* 10(3): 178-185.
- Badr, A. N., M. G. Shehata and A. G. Abdel-Razek (2017b). "Antioxidant activities and potential impacts to reduce aflatoxins utilizing jojoba and jatropa oils and extracts." *International Journal of Pharmacology* 13(8): 1103-1114.
- Bragulat, M., M. Abarca and F. Cabañes (2001). "An easy screening method for fungi producing ochratoxin A in pure culture." *International Journal of Food Microbiology* 71(2-3): 139-144.
- Cortés-Zavaleta, O., A. López-Malo, A. Hernández-Mendoza and H. S. García (2014). "Antifungal activity of lactobacilli and its relationship with 3-phenyllactic acid production." *International Journal of Food Microbiology* 173: 30-35.
- Dagnas, S. and J.-M. Membré (2013). "Predicting and preventing mold spoilage of food products." *Journal of food protection* 76(3): 538-551.
- Dalié, D. K. D., A. M. Deschamps and F. Richard-Forget (2010). "Lactic acid bacteria – Potential for control of mould growth and mycotoxins: A review." *Food Control* 21(4): 370-380.
- De Muynck, C., A. I. Leroy, S. De Maeseneire, F. Arnaut, W. Soetaert and E. J. Vandamme (2004). "Potential of selected lactic acid bacteria to produce food compatible antifungal metabolites." *Microbiological Research* 159(4): 339-346.
- De Vuyst, L. and F. Leroy (2007). "Bacteriocins from lactic acid bacteria: production, purification, and food applications." *Journal of molecular microbiology and biotechnology* 13(4): 194-199.
- Franco, T. S., S. Garcia, E. Y. Hirooka, Y. S. Ono and J. S. dos Santos (2011). "Lactic acid bacteria in the inhibition of *Fusarium graminearum* and deoxynivalenol detoxification." *Journal of Applied Microbiology* 111(3): 739-748.
- Gupta, A., S. K. Tiwari, V. Natrebov and M. L. Chikindas (2016). "Biochemical Properties and Mechanism of Action of Enterocin LD3 Purified from *Enterococcus hirae* LD3." *Probiotics and Antimicrobial Proteins* 8(3): 161-169.
- Gupta, R. and S. Srivastava (2014). "Antifungal effect of antimicrobial peptides (AMPs LR14) derived from *Lactobacillus plantarum* strain LR/14 and their applications in prevention of grain spoilage." *Food Microbiology* 42: 1-7.
- Hassan, M., M. Kjos, I. Nes, D. Diep and F. Lotfipour (2012). "Natural antimicrobial peptides from bacteria: characteristics and potential applications to fight against antibiotic resistance." *Journal of applied microbiology* 113(4): 723-736.
- Hassan, Y. I. and L. B. Bullerman (2008). "Antifungal activity of *Lactobacillus paracasei* ssp. *tolerans* isolated from a sourdough bread culture." *International Journal of Food Microbiology* 121(1): 112-115.
- Hathout, A. S., S. R. Mohamed, A. A. El-Nekeety, N. S. Hassan, S. E. Aly and M. A. Abdel-Wahhab (2011). "Ability of *Lactobacillus casei* and *Lactobacillus reuteri* to protect against oxidative stress in rats fed aflatoxins-contaminated diet." *Toxicon* 58(2): 179-186.
- Hoover, D. G. and S. K. Harlander (1993). Screening methods for detecting bacteriocin activity. *Bacteriocins of lactic acid bacteria*, Elsevier: 23-39.

- Kruger, M. F., M. de Souza Barbosa, A. Miranda, M. Landgraf, M. T. Destro, S. D. Todorov and B. D. G. de Melo Franco (2013). "Isolation of bacteriocinogenic strain of *Lactococcus lactis* subsp. *lactis* from Rocket salad (*Eruca sativa* Mill.) and evidences of production of a variant of nisin with modification in the leader-peptide." *Food control* 33(2): 467-476.
- Kwak, M.-K., R. Liu and S.-O. Kang (2018). "Antimicrobial activity of cyclic dipeptides produced by *Lactobacillus plantarum* LBP-K10 against multidrug-resistant bacteria, pathogenic fungi, and influenza A virus." *Food Control* 85: 223-234.
- Laref, N. and B. Guessas (2013). "Antifungal activity of newly isolates of lactic acid bacteria." *Innov Rom Food Biotechnol* 13: 80-88.
- Lee, S. H. and H. C. Chang (2016). "Isolation of antifungal activity of *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* TA from kimchi and characterization of its antifungal compounds." *Food Science and Biotechnology* 25(1): 213-219.
- Luz, C., F. Saladino, F. Luciano, J. Manes and G. Meca (2017). "In vitro antifungal activity of bioactive peptides produced by *Lactobacillus plantarum* against *Aspergillus parasiticus* and *Penicillium expansum*." *LWT-Food Science and Technology* 81: 128-135.
- Manzoni, P., M. Mostert, M. Leonessa, C. Priolo, D. Farina, C. Monetti, M. Latino and G. Gomirato (2006). "Oral supplementation with *Lactobacillus casei* subspecies *ramnosus* prevents enteric colonization by *Candida* species in preterm neonates: a randomized study." *Clinical infectious diseases* 42(12): 1735-1742.
- Mao, Y., M. Chen and P. Horvath (2015). "*Lactobacillus herbarum* sp. nov., a species related to *Lactobacillus plantarum*." *International journal of systematic and evolutionary microbiology* 65(12): 4682-4688.
- Noonpakdee, W., C. Santivarangkna, P. Jumriangrit, K. Sonomoto and S. Panyim (2003). "Isolation of nisin-producing *Lactococcus lactis* WNC 20 strain from nham, a traditional Thai fermented sausage." *International Journal of Food Microbiology* 81(2): 137-145.
- O'Shea, E. F., P. D. Cotter, C. Stanton, R. P. Ross and C. Hill (2012). "Production of bioactive substances by intestinal bacteria as a basis for explaining probiotic mechanisms: bacteriocins and conjugated linoleic acid." *International journal of food microbiology* 152(3): 189-205.
- Perumal, V., A. Repally, A. Dasari and A. Venkatesan (2016). "Partial purification and characterization of bacteriocin produced by *Enterococcus faecalis* DU10 and its probiotic attributes." *Preparative Biochemistry and Biotechnology* 46(7): 686-694.
- Rogers, L. (1928). "The inhibiting effect of *Streptococcus lactis* on *Lactobacillus bulgaricus*." *Journal of bacteriology* 16(5): 321.
- Ryan, L. A., E. Zannini, F. Dal Bello, A. Pawlowska, P. Koehler and E. K. Arendt (2011). "*Lactobacillus amylovorus* DSM 19280 as a novel food-grade antifungal agent for bakery products." *International journal of food microbiology* 146(3): 276-283.
- Sabry, B. A., A. S. Hathout, A. Nooh, S. E. Aly and M. G. Shehata (2016). "The prevalence of aflatoxin and *Aspergillus parasiticus* in Egyptian sesame seeds." *International Journal of ChemTech Research* 9(11): 308-319.
- Sathe, S. J., N. N. Nawani, P. K. Dhakephalkar and B. P. Kapadnis (2007). "Antifungal lactic acid bacteria with potential to prolong shelf-life of fresh vegetables." *Journal of Applied Microbiology* 103(6): 2622-2628.
- Schnürer, J. and J. Magnusson (2005). "Antifungal lactic acid bacteria as biopreservatives." *Trends in Food Science & Technology* 16(1-3): 70-78.
- Shahat, M. S., A. N. Badr, A. I. Hegazy, S. Ramzy and M. A. Samie (2017). "Reducing the histopathological and biochemical toxicity of aflatoxins contaminated soybean using ozone treatment." *Annual Research and Review in Biology* 15(3).
- Shehata, M., S. El Sohaimy, M. A. El-Sahn and M. Youssef (2016). "Screening of isolated potential probiotic lactic acid bacteria for cholesterol lowering property and bile salt hydrolase activity." *Annals of Agricultural Sciences* 61(1): 65-75.
- Shehata, M. G., A.N. Badr, A.G. Abdel-Razek, M.M. Hassanein, and H.A. Amra (2017). "Oil-bioactive Films as an Antifungal Application to Save Post-harvest Food Crops". *Annual Research and Review in Biology*, 16(4): 1 - 16.
- Stiles, M. E. (1996). "Biopreservation by lactic acid bacteria." *Antonie van Leeuwenhoek* 70(2-4): 331-345.
- Tamura, K., M. Nei and S. Kumar (2004).

- "Prospects for inferring very large phylogenies by using the neighbor-joining method." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 101(30): 11030-11035.
- Ullah, N., X. Wang, J. Wu, Y. Guo, H. Ge, T. Li, S. Khan, Z. Li and X. Feng (2017). "Purification and primary characterization of a novel bacteriocin, LiN333, from *Lactobacillus casei*, an isolate from a Chinese fermented food." *LWT* 84: 867-875.
- Verschuere, L., G. Rombaut, P. Sorgeloos and W. Verstraete (2000). "Probiotic bacteria as biological control agents in aquaculture." *Microbiology and molecular biology reviews* 64(4): 655-671.
- Vijayakumar, P. P. and P. M. Muriana (2015). "A microplate growth inhibition assay for screening bacteriocins against *Listeria monocytogenes* to differentiate their mode-of-action." *Biomolecules* 5(2): 1178-1194.
- Wang, H., Y. Yan, J. Wang, H. Zhang and W. Qi (2012). "Production and Characterization of Antifungal Compounds Produced by *Lactobacillus plantarum* IMAU10014." *PLoS ONE* 7(1): e29452.
- Wang, Y., L. Wang, F. Liu, Q. Wang, J. N. Selvaraj, F. Xing, Y. Zhao and Y. Liu (2016). "Ochratoxin A Producing Fungi, Biosynthetic Pathway and Regulatory Mechanisms." *Toxins* 8(3): 83.
- Wen, L. S., K. Philip and N. Ajam (2016). "Purification, characterization and mode of action of plantaricin K25 produced by *Lactobacillus plantarum*." *Food Control* 60: 430-439.
- Yan, F., H. Cao, T. L. Cover, R. Whitehead, M. K. Washington and D. B. Polk (2007). "Soluble proteins produced by probiotic bacteria regulate intestinal epithelial cell survival and growth." *Gastroenterology* 132(2): 562-575.
- Yang, E. and H. Chang (2010). "Purification of a new antifungal compound produced by *Lactobacillus plantarum* AF1 isolated from kimchi." *International journal of food microbiology* 139(1-2): 56-63.
- Yi, L., Y. Dang, J. Wu, L. Zhang, X. Liu, B. Liu, Y. Zhou and X. Lu (2016). "Purification and characterization of a novel bacteriocin produced by *Lactobacillus crustorum* MN047 isolated from koumiss from Xinjiang, China." *Journal of Dairy Science* 99(9): 7002-7015.